

PROSPECTS OF MODERN MATERIAL SCIENCE AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN AGRICULTURE

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Annotation: This article is based on concrete facts about material science, the low, present and future of material science. Opinions are expressed about semiconductor materials, which are part of material science, and about their current state, as well as about the fact that equipment and devices created on the basis of these materials have penetrated into all spheres of our life and about the prospects for their development.

Key words: materials science, fundamental, experimental, metals, dielectrics, semiconductors, silicon, germanium, technology, Solid Solution, technology, vacuum electronics, synthesis

INTRODUCTION

Materials science is the science of the nature of the properties of materials, the order of the ways of their management and the creation of various materials with a combination of the best and acceptable properties.

The creation of new materials determined the development of the stage of development for many centuries, and it will remain so after that. Only as a result of the development of fundamental Sciences and experimental techniques, material science has become a level of Science, the importance of which in all respects increases at a very high rate.

Among the tasks related to the creation of devices based on metals, increasing the efficiency of human physical labor, since the 40s of the XX century, first of all, the problems of creating devices, increasing the efficiency of human mental labor, began to be of particular importance.

The solution to this problem was found thanks to the creation and large-scale implementation of materials that are representatives of a specific new class: dielectrics and semiconductors.

The most common and sufficiently studied of semiconductor materials and compounds used on an industrial scale, as well as their solid solutions, and for the production of promising devices of a new type GaAs, GaP, InP, CdTe, CdS, SnS - $A^3 B^5$ - and $A^2 B^6$ for the study of the properties of their compounds - are intensively carried out scientific research.

Material and Methods

Currently, as a result of the use of these materials: in computing and computerization, in the field of long-distance communication techniques, in

methods of data storage and transmission, in the improvement of information technologies, in the process of converting energy from one type to another, in achieving a high efficiency value of the useful coefficient of work, in automating production, in - there was an opportunity to realize the achievement of sustainable development achievements, which leaves an excellent foundation in creating renewable and environmentally friendly energy sources and transferring household appliances to the basis of electronics.

The solution to these issues is the implementation of ways to change rapidly and extremely rapidly occurring processes, that is, the migration and behavior of electrical charges, electric and magnetic fields in surface bodies, optical and sound waves, at the set level and in order; the field of techniques: electronics, micro and nanoelectronics constitute the main essence.

Until the end of the 40 s of the XX century, these tasks were performed by vacuum devices, the movement of hard-melting metal cathodes from the Surface, generated by the emission of free charge carriers, directed towards the anode, controlled by wakkum electronics as a result of changing the electric field laid.

Due to the development of computing techniques, radio and television devices, the requirements for the speed of movement of automatic means and the extension of the service life increased rapidly, while the number of devices in electronic circuits also increased.

Under these conditions, the following disadvantages related to vacuum electronics have become obvious: a small (low) speed of movement (no greater than millisecond), a low level of useful working coefficient (2-5%), and at the same time a lot of energy consumption and a high cost, a large amount of heat separation, which prevents the devices from making their dimensions too small, Thus, the development of the technique motivated the search for new ways to control the types and movement of charge carriers, the behavior of physical fields of different types. This research led to the invention of a new device at the end of the 40s and beginning of the 50s of the XX century, that is, a transistor that occurs directly in a solid state, transporting various pointing charges.

As a result, there was a transition from vacuum electronics to solid-state electronics, which not only lost its shortcomings in vacuum electronics, but also had a number of advantages.

Ultimately, the creation - synthesis of semiconductor materials caused the creation of an unusually promising situation in the development of electronics.

The extraction of solid-solution materials based on silicon, germanium

semiconductor elements, as well as and compounds, and the creation of modern semiconductor devices served as a powerful impetus for the development of this industry.

Now there was an opportunity to change the concentration of charge carriers to several modes - to purposefully change the electrical conductivity. The creation of a field in which a solid directly touches charge carriers with different conductivity was carried out (p-N-transition), which in turn serves to correct currents, to register and amplify electrical signals. p - n-transitions form the basis of a wide range of solid-state electronics devices. If we add to this again that the speed of operation of devices created on the basis of solid - state electronics in comparison with vacuum electronics devices works in nano-and pico-seconds (10^{-9} and 10^{-12} s), we will realize how wide the possibilities of this industry are. Taking into account the fact that the useful working coefficient of these devices is much higher and there is an opportunity to greatly shrink (miniaturize) devices, we will be able to clearly feel the unequal advantage of devices created on the basis of solid-state electronics in front of devices created on the basis of vacuum electronics.

The material that is considered important at the moment and in the near future and is produced in large quantities in industry and is widely used in various fields of Electronics is Silicon (equivalent to 30% of the Earth's crust). Around the world, the production of polycrystalline silicon semiconductor is increasing year by year, and at present it is around 15 thousand tons per year, while monocrystalline silicon is the most widely used and important field of Electronics-the microelectronics field, which is produced around 10 thousand tons per year.

With microelectronics and its development, the capabilities of Computer Science, Computer Science, television, communications (including in the long range), household and special equipment are closely related.

The synthesis of semiconductor compounds, as noted above: GaAs, GaP, CdTe, CdS, ZnS and others - plays a huge role in Solid-State Electronics the acquisition of these compounds on silicon and germanium bases, which are typical representatives of the semiconductor family of elements of the fourth group, also increases their attractiveness.

The role of solid-state electronics devices in energy: the transfer of electrical energy (including over long distances) using semiconductor converters leaves an excellent.

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The remarkable and unique properties of absolute large quantities of semiconductors are very low if the concentration of random alien substances affecting the electrical conductivity of the semiconductors in them does not exceed $10^{10} - 10^{13}$ at/cm³ i.e. $10^{-7} - 10^{-3}$ % (at.), and the crystal structure is perfect, manifested only if it is extremely high. The synthesis of semiconductor substances in modern Microelectronics, as well as the implementation of the above works, would remain a raw fantasy without epitaxial technologies.

With the improvement of epitaxial technology, integrated circuits have an increased level of integration (i.e. the number of devices in one crystal) and the positioning density of devices (in 1 cm², in the future the number of devices in 1 cm³). The transition from one of the circuits to another without matching is also improving: integral scheme (IS), large integrated circuit (KIS), ultra-large integrated circuit (O'KIS) and ultra-large (super large) integrated circuit (O'KIS). Currently, the linear size of one device in such a scheme is approximately 200 times smaller than the thickness of human hair with a degree of integration (i.e., the number of devices in one device).

Hence, the rapid development of materials science or the electronic industry requires us to create promising solid solutions based on the elementary system, which are typical representatives of semiconductors with fundamentally new electrophysical, photoelectric and optical properties, and the properties of which are comprehensively studied.

In place of the conclusion, it can be said that today there is practically no inaccessible area of \ u200b \ u200bThe penetration of devices made on the basis of semiconductors.

The role of semiconductors in training is incomparably greater. Because, the basis of most laboratory instruments that are carried out to consolidate our theoretical knowledge is semiconductor devices. Widely used in agriculture: modern thermometers, moisture meter, various sensors (sensors) that measure illumination between plants.

The basis of meteostans in agrometeorological posts is semiconductor devices. The widespread use of modern innovative technologies, devices in the agrarian sphere, of course, serves as an auxiliary factor in the broad sense of finding a solution to food insecurity. Intelligent agriculture, agricultural digitization all this is carried out on the basis of devices and instruments made on the basis of semiconductor materials.

On the basis of devices that analyze the composition of the soil, devices that determine the composition of water and its consumption, devices that monitor and combat agricultural pests, devices that diagnose ultrasound on animals, devices for quality drying of agricultural products, laser devices used in land leveling and many other devices, semiconductor materials lie. Hence, the prospects for the field of materials science and its semiconductors are much higher.

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